

Scaling Approach to Obtaining the Tsallis Distributions

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In a previous note (1), we obtained the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from a scaling argument based on: $E_{ave} = \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e) \} / \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e) \}$, where $p(e)$ is unnormalized and one works in three dimensions. The scaling feature follows from $e \rightarrow T e/T$ so that $E = \text{Number} * T$. Now, one may change $T \rightarrow T+dT$ and Number should not change, but the integral creating Number involves T and so one may replace T with $T+dT$ and show that the coefficient of dT is 0. Using this approach in (1), one may explicitly find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from a differential equation.

Here we try to apply this approach to the Tsallis distribution. In this case, one has: $E_{ave} = \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e)^q \} / \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e)^q \}$, where $p(e)$ is unnormalized and one works in three dimensions. The scaling approach leads to a differential equation (sitting inside an integral $(0, \infty) c_1 \sqrt{e} de$) again. The approximation used in (1), namely that e ranges from 0 to infinite is again used.

For $q=1$, one may show that the differential equation yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. If one suggests that for e/T large and $q \neq 1$, that one should obtain a power series: $(e/T)^b$, then the differential equation coefficient of dT shows that $b = 1/(1-q)$. From the $q=1 \exp(-e/T)$ condition and the power law for large e/T , one may obtain the Tsallis solution $(1 - (1-q) e/T)^{1/(1-q)}$ using scaling.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Scaling Approach

This approach has been discussed in (1) in detail and so we provide a brief overview here. We consider:

$$E_{ave} = \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e) \} / \{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} p(e) de \} \quad ((1))$$

for $p(e)$ unnormalized and work in three dimensions so that $pp dp \rightarrow c_1 \sqrt{e} de$.

One may then write: $e = e/T T$ so that

$$E_{ave} = T * \text{Number} \quad ((2))$$

We make that approximation that e ranges from 0 to infinite. Thus, an explicit approximation is required for the scaling approach. This is the same approximation used for elastic two body scattering:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ if } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((3))$$

If $T \rightarrow T+dT$, one may replace T in e/T with $T+dT$ in the integral used to calculate Number and find an integral-differential equation in dp/dy (where $y=e/T$). As shown in (1), the solution of this

integral-differential equation is $p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$. In (1) we worked explicitly in 3-dimensions. Here we try to apply this approach to the Tsallis distribution.

Tsallis Distribution from a Scaling Approach

In the Tsallis case, we use:

$$E_{ave} = \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de e p(e)^{\text{power } q} \right\} / \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de p(e)^{\text{power } q} \right\} \quad ((4))$$

Here q is a parameter and $p(e)$ is not normalized. The above $p(e)^{\text{power } q}$ is a standard approach used in the Tsallis case. We also note that the idea of the Tsallis distribution is:

$$\text{For } q=1, p(e) \rightarrow \exp(-e/T) \text{ and for } q \neq 1 \text{ and } e/T \gg 1 \quad p(e) = e^{\text{power } b(q)} \quad ((5))$$

We will ultimately use ((5)) in obtaining an explicit Tsallis form for $p(e)$. We also use the approximation that e ranges from 0 to infinite.

We first write:

$$E_{ave} = T * \text{Number} = T * \int_{(0, \text{infinite})} c_1 \sqrt{e} de (y+dy)^{(p+dy dp/dy)^{\text{power } q}} / \left\{ \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de (p+dy dp/dy)^{\text{power } q} \right\} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Here } y=e/T \text{ and the } dy = -y (dT/T) \quad ((7))$$

Note: dT/T sits outside the integral, but y does not because it contains e and the integral is over de .

We write the denominator as: $N_1 + N_2 \int c_1 \sqrt{e} de y dp/dy$ and use: $1/(1+d) \approx 1-d$, for d tiny. The coefficient of dT then becomes:

$$0 = \text{Number}^3 q y dp/dy - p^{\text{power } q} y - q y y dp/dy p^{\text{power } (q-1)} \quad ((8))$$

One may note that each term in ((8)) sits inside an integral $\int_{(0, \text{infinite})} c_1 \sqrt{e} de$.

We first consider the $q=1$ case which should yield $p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$ as in (1). In such a case, one has:

$$\text{Number}^3 y dp/dy - py - yy dp/dy = 0 \quad ((9))$$

In (1) we used integration by parts on the $yy dp/dy$ term in ((9)) and were able to explicitly calculate Number^3 for a solution of $\exp(-y) = \exp(-e/T)$. In particular, after integrating the $yy dp/dy$ term by parts one has a yp term and so $p = \exp(-y)$ means that dp/dy in the first term also become a number multiplied by py and so one need only check that the coefficients add to zero which they do as explicitly shown in (1).

The next check is to consider: $p = y^b$ ((10))

where b is unknown, but presumed to be a function of q .

Using ((8)) we have:

$$b y^b - y^{(qb+1)} - b y^{(qb+1)} = 0 \quad ((11))$$

For ((11)) to hold, the coefficient of each given power of y must be 0. Given that the first term is y^b , at least one other y^b term is needed to cancel it, but if the third term is not y^b , then its coefficient must be 0, which it is not. Thus, all three terms must be y^b . We find then that:

$$b = 1/(1-q) \quad ((12)) \text{ so that all three terms are } y^b$$

Thus, one wishes to have a $p(e)$ unnormalized which becomes $\exp(-y)$ for $q=1$ and y^b for $q \neq 1$ and $e/T = y \gg 1$, where $b = 1/(1-q)$.

We consider a linear function of y to the power $1/(1-q)$.

$$(a_1 + a_2 y)^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((13))$$

When $q=1$, $1/(1-q)$ diverges so one may use: $a_1=1$ and $a_2 = -(1-q)$ ((14)) so that one obtains $p = \exp(-y)$ for $q=1$.

$$\text{Thus, we obtain: } p(e)_{\text{Tsallis unnormalized}} = (1 - (1-q)y)^{1/(1-q)} \text{ for } y=e/T \quad ((15))$$

using the scaling approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we show that a scaling approach may be used to find the unnormalized Tsallis distribution $p(e) = (1 - (1-q)e/T)^{1/(1-q)}$. We start with an expression for Eave for the Tsallis case ((4)) and write $e = e/T$, $T = y T$. Thus, $E_{ave} = T \cdot \text{Number}$, if one allows e to range from 0 to infinite (which is an approximation). This is the same approximation used in (1) for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. We then replace T with $T+dT$ in the integral which creates "Number" and expand to first order in dT . We argue, as in (1), that the coefficient of dT , a differential equation sitting inside the integral $\int_0^\infty c_1 \sqrt{e} de$, must be 0. In the Tsallis case, we argue that for $q=1$, one must obtain $p = \exp(-y) = \exp(-e/T)$, the MB result, but that for $q \neq 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$, one should have $p = y^b$, where b is some function of q . We use the differential equation (sitting inside the integral) to find $b = 1/(1-q)$. We then postulate a linear function $(a_1 + a_2 y)^{1/(1-q)}$ such that for $y \gg 1$ it becomes $a_2 y^{1/(1-q)}$ and for $q=1$, it

becomes $\exp(-y)$. This leads to $a_1=1$ and $a_2 = -(1-q)$. Thus, the scaling approach may be used to find the Tsallis distribution, we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Using Scaling Parts 1 and 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2026)